

ProCleanLakes

Readme file

**20251013-ProCleanLakes-
Assessment of Geo-environmental
Status of Trichonis Lake, Greece:
Mineralogy, Sedimentology, and
Chemistry - ISBN (print) 978-618-
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Reason(s) for data analysis: *The data was collected within project ProCleanLakes which investigates, the geo-environmental status of Lake Trichonis, Greece.*

Creation date of file: 11/2025

Used method(s): *Assessment of the geo-environmental status of Trichonis Lake by analyzing the mineralogical and sedimentological characteristics of its sediments along with the physicochemical parameters of lake water.*

Used software (incl. version and add-ons) and tools:

- Folk's methodology and classification
- X-Ray Siemens D 5005 Diffractometer
- DIFFRACplus software package at NKUA
- HACH DR/2400 spectrometer
- Multiparameter Analyzer (CyberScan Series 600, EUTECH)

Data: *None*

Code: *None*

Additional files: *None*

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Notes:

- *Non-anonymized data is available from the creators for secondary analysis.*